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Executive Summary

This document is the second Annual Report from the Digital Twin of the Ocean for Arctic Fisheries (ARCFISH) project. ARCFISH is a project funded by the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP) program through five national funding agencies in Europe. ARCFISH develops a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) to support the Blue Economy by way of sustainable fisheries in the Arctic, focusing on two key regions: (1) Western Greenland, centred around Disko Bay, and (2) region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and the Barents Sea. In the Arctic, sustainable fisheries are crucial for long-term ecosystem and community resilience. Traditional commercial activities have had negative impacts such as overfishing, pollution, habitat destruction, and climate change have adversely affected ocean health, resulting in declining fish stocks and loss of biodiversity. New data products and services, co-developed with stakeholders, are needed for better decision-making in fisheries management towards a sustainable Blue Economy. For example, in Disko Bay, ecosystem indices could include spatial maps of zooplankton, benthos, shrimp biomass, and upwelling areas. Fisheries and fleet data from Iceland to the Barents Sea could be integrated into the DTO. Potential new services include advanced eLogbooks and spatiotemporal pattern detection and visualization, leveraging digital technologies for cost-efficiency.

Highlights from the second year of the project include:

- Continued dialogue with stakeholders elaborating requirements and demonstrating first results.
- Extended set of data products generated using the upgraded workflow engine.
- First examples of new data products generated using the enhanced ecosystem model and workflow engine.
- Updated and new data products ingested in the DTO for user demonstrations and feedback.
- Enhanced capabilities of the DTO workflow engine.
- Improved functionality of the Digital Twin platform, including ingestion and visualisation of new data sources.
- Initial testing and feedback on the developed DTO solution and data products.
- Growing outreach and dissemination – Increased visibility at conferences and community events and customised brochures for case study regions.
- Future work planned – Further enhancements of ARCFISH data products, services and DTO platform.

Deliverables produced in year 2 include:

- D2.2 Data ingestion services V2 (Beszczynska-Moeller et al., 2025)
- D3.1 Data products for sustainable fisheries (Maar et al., 2025)
- D4.3 Blue Insight DTO V2 - Examples of data and functionality (Hestnes, 2026)
- D5.4 Report on DEC activities Year 2 (Higgins et al., 2026)
- D6.2 Annual Report Year 1 (Hamre et al., 2025)

Deliverables and other digital material are available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/arcfish/>.

More information on the project can be found at: <https://www.arcfish.eu/>.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
AREX	A long-term, large-scale Arctic monitoring programme focused on the Nordic Seas and the European Arctic
AWE	Automatic Workflow Engine
BGC	Biogeochemical
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service
CORA	Coriolis Ocean Dataset for Reanalysis
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
FlexSem	Flexible System for Marine modeling
GEM	Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring
GeoJSON	Geographic JavaScript Object Notation
GEOTIFF	Geographic Tagged Image File Format
NetCDF	Network Common Data Format
NRT	Near Real Time
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OPeNDAP	Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol
SBE	Sustainable Blue Economy
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
THREDDS	Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Services
TOPAZ5	Towards an Operational Prediction system for the North Atlantic European coastal Zones modelling engine, version 5
TOR	Task Orchestrator fRamework
WAM	WAVE Model

1. Continued stakeholder engagement and first demonstrations

The ARCFISH project develops a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) to support sustainable fisheries in the Arctic, using the Blue Insight platform. The Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE) promotes sustainable development and conservation of ocean resources for economic, social, and environmental benefits. The project focuses on long-term sustainability and resilience of ocean ecosystems and communities in Western Greenland (Disko Bay) and the region around Iceland, northwards to Svalbard and the Barents Sea. Close collaboration with stakeholders, including fishers, seafood processors, researchers, authorities, and policymakers, is essential. The project is involving stakeholders throughout the development process, ensuring the final product meets end-user expectations. To avoid stakeholder fatigue, partners are prioritizing stakeholders based on their expertise, interest, and expectations, following a suggested protocol to maintain fruitful dialogue within the targeted regions and the wider Arctic science and fisheries communities.

1.1. Stakeholder engagement strategy

The engagement strategy was designed to ensure early and continuous involvement of relevant stakeholders, while avoiding consultation fatigue and maintaining a clear link between stakeholder input and technical development.

The first year focused primarily on identifying stakeholders, understanding user needs, and defining requirements for data, functionality, and services. Stakeholders were selected and prioritised based on their relevance to the two case study regions—Western Greenland (Disko Bay) and the Icelandic region extending towards the Barents Sea—as well as their roles within the fisheries sector, research community, management authorities, and technology providers. Engagement activities consisted mainly of bilateral meetings, small group discussions, and early workshops, allowing for open dialogue and detailed feedback. These interactions were used to explore key challenges faced by stakeholders, such as access to environmental information, interpretation of ecosystem variability, operational constraints, and decision-making needs in fisheries management. Emphasis was placed on understanding how integrated environmental, ecosystem, and fisheries-dependent data could add value to existing practices.

The second project year focused on moving from requirements gathering to demonstration and validation of emerging Digital Twin functionality. Stakeholder engagement during this period centred on interactions at key scientific, policy, and industry events (see section 1.2), where prototype data products and workflows were presented and discussed. These activities align with the overall workshop plan (Figure 1), bridging early exploratory engagement and the final phase of structured validation and uptake through targeted end-user workshops.

Figure 1. Engaging with stakeholders in the two case study regions through a series of workshops and meetings.

1.2. Stakeholder workshops and events

During the second year of the project, the ARCFISH DTO and developed products were presented and discussed at several major events for stakeholders in the two targeted case study regions.

Iceland case study

ARCFISH developments were presented at two major events:

Iceland Stakeholder meeting 2025, 14 October, Reykjavik, Iceland

The meeting was organised by MATIS and Trackwell. Stakeholders from Brim, Iceland Seafood, Fisheries Iceland, Ministry of the Environment, Marine and Freshwater Research Institute participated. The participants in the meeting are involved in several similar projects in relation to mitigating and adopting to climate changes in the fisheries sector. Talks about what data from other projects is relevant and beneficial to implement into DTO.

Read more at: <https://www.arcfish.eu/post/arcfish-in-dialogue-with-icelandic-stakeholders>

Seafood Conference Iceland (Sjávarútvegsráðstefnan) 2025, 6-7 November, Reykjavik, Iceland

The project participated in the Sjávarútvegsráðstefnan (Seafood Conference Iceland), presenting work on Arctic fisheries and engaging with a broad range of stakeholders from the Icelandic seafood sector. Participants included fishers, seafood processors, researchers, technology providers, and European and national policymakers. Interactions focused on sustainable Arctic fisheries, the use of environmental data and modelling, and how digital tools such as Digital Twins of the Ocean can support fisheries management and policy-relevant decision-making.

Read more at: <https://www.arcfish.eu/post/arcfish-at-the-iceland-seafood-conference>

Greenland case study

Presenting ARCFISH developments and engaging with stakeholders focused on the

23rd Danish Marine Science Meeting 2026, 20–22 January, Helsingør, Denmark

The conference featured presentations by Marie Maar and Vibe Schourup-Kristensen (Aarhus University), who spoke on, “Decade of Ocean Science: Predictions and management scenarios using Digital Twins of the Ocean for Greenland, Faroe Islands and Denmark,” and “Modeling Shrimp Larval Drift in Disko Bay: Linking Ocean Dynamics and Recruitment in a Changing Arctic,” respectively, as well as Magnus Grøtterud (Kongsberg Discovery), who delivered a talk titled “Towards Digital Twins of the Arctic.” Kongsberg Discovery also hosted an information booth during the meeting, where participants had the opportunity to learn more about the ARCFISH Digital Twin and discuss its development with the team. A Danish version of the ARCFISH brochure was prepared specifically to reach Danish and Greenlandic stakeholders (see Figure 17). The event brought together an estimated 500 participants.

Read more at: <https://www.arcfish.eu/post/23rd-danish-marine-science-meeting>

2. Extended functionality of the ARCFISH DTO

2.1. Data ingestion and visualisation

During the past year, ARCFISH has significantly expanded the data ingestion and visualisation capabilities of its Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), built on the Blue Insight platform. These developments strengthen the project’s ability to integrate heterogeneous environmental, ecosystem, and fisheries-dependent data streams and to deliver actionable information for sustainable Arctic fisheries.

Development of OPeNDAP-based data ingestion in ARCFISH has focused on enabling seamless access to large, distributed scientific datasets without the need for local storage or full file downloads. Blue Insight now natively supports Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) interfaces and has been expanded with full OPeNDAP integration, allowing users to connect directly to remote THREDDS servers. The new data loading interface (Figure 2) provides a unified entry point where users can browse multiple data sources, including OGC feature APIs, local files, cloud optimised GeoTIFFs, and OPeNDAP endpoints. Once a dataset is selected from a THREDDS server, the system presents flexible ingestion options (Figure 3), enabling users to load data as point clouds for filtering and analysis, as gridded map layers (Figure 4), or to download subsets for further processing through the Analytics Workflow Engine (AWE) presented in Section 2.2.

Figure 2 Data loading screen enabling data integration from several sources using OPeNDAP.

Load data

Load OGC Features

- > (https://thredds.met.no/thredds/fou-hi/.../myocean/SeaWAM4km/SeaWAM4km-2023-10-29/catalog.xml)
- > (cmems/cmems_obs-si_arc_phy_int_1km-svb_P1D-in)
- > (sea_ice/SeaWAM4km-ARC-SEAICE-HR-OBS-ice_conc_svalbard_aggregated)
- > (https://thredds.met.no/thredds/fou-hi/.../myocean/ARC-MFC/thredds/catalog/myocean/arc-mfc/arc-metno-arctic20-roms/catalog.xml)
- > (arctic20/dataset-arctic20-roms-arc-myocean-be)
- ▼ (https://thredds.met.no/thredds/fou-hi/fou-hi.xml)
 - > Ocean and Sea Ice
 - ▼ Waves
 - > met.no MyWaveWAM8km Nordic Seas wave forecasting system (best estimate) (deprecated after Feb 11, 2020)
 - > met.no WAVEWATCH III 4km Regional wave forecasting system (latest and archive)
 - ▼ met.no MyWaveWAM4km Nordic Seas wave forecasting system (archive and best estimate) (Production ends June 6, 2023)
 - ▼ MyWaveWam4km wave model
 - ▼ met.no MyWaveWam4km files (Cycle 4.7) (Production end 2023-10-29)
 - ▼ met.no MyWaveWam4km forecast archive
 - ▼ met.no MyWaveWam4km CurLo4_5 files (Production end 2023-11-10)

Realtime

Load Sensor Data

WMS Layers

ID	mywavewam4_be
Name	met.no MyWaveWam4km Aggregation Best Estimates (Cycle 4.7) (Production end 2023-10-29)
URL Path	sea/mywavewam4/mywavewam4_be
Data Type	GRID
Data Format	
Data Size	
Date	
Metadata Service Name	
Metadata Data Format	
Metadata Inherited	true

Access

OPeNDAP [Load](#) [OPeNDAP Dataset Query form](#)

WMS [Add layers](#) [WMS GetCapabilities](#)

HTTP [Download](#)

Figure 3 Data loader screen presenting multiple options for the user.

Figure 4 Sea ice thickness and vessel tracks loaded as layers. The map viewer can replay the time if the data has a time component.

2.2. Analytics Workflow Engine (AWE)

Development of the AWE has been central to automating and streamlining data ingestion workflows in the ARCFISH Digital Twin of the Ocean. AWE replaces the earlier TOR framework, offering a more powerful and flexible system for orchestrating routine data fetching, processing, and transformation tasks. Users can create workflows in AWE using either a Graphical User Interface (GUI), as illustrated in Figure 5, or by specifying the different steps in the workflow using a file format called JavaScript Object Notation, as illustrated in Figure 6. In both cases the code needed in each step is pre-packaged in a Docker container with required libraries and other utilities.

AWE has been essential for developing scheduled ingestion workflows for major operational products, such as the TOPAZ5 10-day sea surface temperature and ice–ocean forecasts (Figure 7). These automated routines extract, subset, and merge model outputs into time series files suitable for direct visualisation in Blue Insight. Collectively, AWE has enabled robust, repeatable, and scalable ingestion pipelines that underpin the expanding analytical capabilities of the ARCFISH DTO. Examples of new data products ingested in the DTO using workflows developed in AWE are shown in Section 3.

Figure 5 AWE interface with the workflow defined as a sequence of steps. Each step carries out a specific task, receiving input from earlier steps or environment variable, and passing its results onto the next step in the workflow. The user can start new runs of a workflow through the GUI, track their progress and inspect the log files being written as the processing is carried out.

netcdf_opendap_topaz:0.3.0_imported_1760109001410_testingcombine

← Back Copy ID Export Launch Flow

Flow Summary

Flow ID: netcdf_opendap_topaz:0.3.0_imported_1760109001410_testingcombine
 Tasks: 3
 Inputs Required: 0 variables

Recent Runs

Refresh View All

- 9475d2e48a7b467e817d616b8757f0a7
12/01/2026, 01:30:00
TimeTriggered-opendap_imported_1762182372749 Completed
- 5555265a41bd4b5caacbd785886b7ada
11/01/2026, 01:30:00
TimeTriggered-opendap_imported_1762182372749 Completed
- 4cd9da1de1804ac78495700e4c3084d4
10/01/2026, 01:30:00
TimeTriggered-opendap_imported_1762182372749 Completed
- 83cb2e6a75084b9a9a634bd9f837d316
09/01/2026, 01:30:00
TimeTriggered-opendap_imported_1762182372749 Completed
- 52172e4c3120434a9ba8c27ae78499fa
08/01/2026, 01:30:00
TimeTriggered-opendap_imported_1762182372749 Completed

Flow Configuration

Flow Name: netcdf_opendap_topaz Tag: 0.3.0_imported_1760109001410_testingcombine

Full Flow ID: netcdf_opendap_topaz:0.3.0_imported_1760109001410_testingcombine

Tasks

- Get names for topaz filelink dockerContainer
- Filter and download netcdf file using openDAP dockerContainer
- Combine newly created netCDF files dockerContainer

Figure 6 Screenshot of the TOPAZ5 extraction service running in AWE at a given time every day. The time shown in the screenshot is in local time (CET), but the workflow specification defines the trigger time in UTC to ensure the service is run at the appropriate time regardless of changes in local time (e.g. summer time).

Figure 7 Visualisation of sea surface temperature forecast from the TOPAZ5 model in Blue Insight, including trawling activity data from the Brim fishery, marked as short lines in the visualization.

3. Updated and new data products

A major advance in data ingestion is the implementation of robust workflows supporting both in situ and model-derived data. Selected examples of data products ingested in the last year are described in the following subsections.

The platform now ingests oceanographic measurements from long-term monitoring programmes such as AREX and GEM, as well as large-scale observational networks like Argo (Figure 8, Figure 9). New ingestion services automatically process Argo temperature and salinity profiles, interpolate them onto standard depths, and prepare them for near-real-time visualisation. Similar ingestion pipelines have been established for CORA temperature–salinity reanalysis fields from the Copernicus Marine Service, making extensive historical and NRT datasets available in the ARCFISH DTO.

Model-based ingestion has also advanced, with automated workflows for daily TOPAZ5 met ice ocean forecasts (Figure 7) and twice-daily WAVE Model (WAM) forecasts (Figure 13). These workflows operate within the new AWE, enabling scheduled updates, subsetting, and standardised preparation of outputs for interactive visualisation. Additionally, the ingestion of ecosystem model output from the FlexSem

Disko Bay model—including multiyear fields of physical and biogeochemical variables—allows users to explore spatio-temporal ecological patterns directly within the Blue Insight platform (Figure 9).

3.1. In situ oceanographic data from the Argo program

Data from selected Argo floats were ingested into Blue Insight through OPeNDAP. In addition, a workflow was developed to regularly extract and update regional Argo observations in CSV format for ingestion into the DTO. The workflow retrieves high-quality core variables—pressure, temperature, and salinity—from 2020 accessing daily updated sources such as the Ifremer’s ERDDAP and GDAC servers. To handle large volumes efficiently, data are fetched in parallel and cached, then aggregated, converted from individual points into vertical profiles, and interpolated onto standard 10 dbar pressure levels.

Within the DTO platform, users can filter Argo data by depth, time, and location, enabling visualisation of variables such as surface temperature or salinity at specific levels and periods (Figures 8+9). Future steps include fully automating the workflow using AWE and extending the workflow to include biogeochemical Argo (BGC) variables, which will add valuable environmental context despite their lower data density.

Figure 8 Temperature data at the surface (at the standard level of 0 dbar) from all Argo profiles collected in the Iceland region in the period 1.01.2020-4.02.2026, ingested into Blue Insight and shown with bathymetry in the background.

Figure 9 Salinity at the standard level of 10 dbar from all Argo profiles collected in the Iceland region in the period 1.01.2020-4.02.2026, ingested into Blue Insight filtered to show only data from 2024.

3.2. In situ oceanographic data from the GEM program

In situ oceanographic data from the Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) programme constitute a critical long-term observational foundation for understanding Arctic marine ecosystems and their response to climate variability. GEM is an integrated monitoring and research programme that has operated since 1995, bringing together Danish and Greenlandic institutions to collect interdisciplinary data on ecosystem processes and climate feedbacks across Greenland. The programme currently covers several key regions, including Zackenberg, Kobbefjord (Nuuk), and Disko Bay, with more than 1,000 physical, chemical, and biological parameters made openly available through the GEM database.

Within the ARCFISH data ingestion framework, particular emphasis has been placed on marine observations from Disko Bay, a highly productive and well-studied Arctic coastal system that is central to fisheries and ecosystem research. GEM data from Disko Bay include CTD measurements of temperature and salinity, as well as biogeochemical variables such as nutrients (nitrate, nitrite, ammonium, silicate, phosphate), chlorophyll a, pH, dissolved inorganic carbon, suspended particulate matter, and indicators of macroalgae growth. These observations provide essential environmental context for ecosystem modelling and fisheries-related analyses.

As a concrete implementation, temperature and salinity measurements from GEM cruises conducted between 2018 and 2024 were retrieved from the GEM database and prepared for ingestion into the Blue Insight platform. Original text-based data files were standardised, reformatted, and converted into GeoJSON, ensuring consistent geographical referencing and selection of key variables (date, depth,

temperature, salinity). Both individual yearly datasets and a combined multi-year dataset were generated, enabling flexible visualisation and efficient exploration of temporal variability.

Once ingested, GEM data can be visualised as spatial point layers, filtered by depth and time, and compared across years within the same interface (Figure 10). This capability supports detailed assessment of interannual changes in hydrographic conditions and strengthens the linkage between long-term observations, model outputs, and fisheries-relevant analyses. Looking ahead, the ingestion and conversion workflows for GEM data can be further automated using the platform’s workflow engine, and additional biogeochemical GEM variables are planned for inclusion to enrich the environmental baseline for Arctic fisheries applications.

Figure 10 Visualisation of temperature at 10 m depth from GEM cruises in Disko Bay (2018–2024) in Blue Insight. Cruise data are collated into a single GeoJSON file, with station details for date, depth, and measured variables (temperature and salinity).

3.3. NRT In situ oceanographic data from the Copernicus Marine Data Store

The CORA Near Real Time (NRT) product (INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_OA_NRT_013_002) provides recent global temperature and salinity observations, available from 1 January 2023 to 1 October 2025. It is produced by the Coriolis team using the In Situ Analysis System (ISAS), which applies objective analysis methods to quality-controlled measurements from diverse observing platforms, including Argo floats, CTDs, XBTs, moorings, drifting buoys, and instrumented marine mammals. NRT fields are delivered as gridded datasets suitable for monitoring seasonal and short-term variability and for validating operational ocean models. For ARCFISH, selected NRT subsets were downloaded via Python/Jupyter tools in NetCDF format and converted to GeoJSON. Monthly temperature and salinity fields at 1 m depth — such as those shown for January 2024—were ingested and displayed as coloured point layers (Figure 11, Figure 12). Although depth levels are currently handled as separate files, future versions will integrate depth as a native dimension.

Figure 11 CORA NRT temperature and salinity data at depth of 1m loaded as layers into the scene. Salinity in January 2024 is displayed. The data has a time component and can be shown for other months of 2024.

Figure 12 CORA NRT temperature data at depth of 1m and 300m loaded as layers into the scene. The datasets have a time component and are displayed for April 2024.

3.4. Model products from Copernicus Marine Service

Wave forecast products from the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) are ingested to provide near-real-time information on sea state conditions relevant for Arctic marine operations and fisheries. The wave forecasts are generated using the WAM, which delivers high resolution (≈ 3 km) forecasts of surface wave parameters, including significant wave height, peak wave period, and mean wave direction. Forecasts are produced twice daily and provide hourly outputs for 5- and 10-day forecast horizons.

To support efficient use within the digital platform, a dedicated automated ingestion workflow has been implemented to extract WAM forecast data via OPeNDAP access provided by CMEMS. The workflow subsets the data spatially and temporally for selected areas of interest and parameters, reducing data volume while preserving essential forecast information. Daily forecast files are merged into continuous time-series datasets and stored in NetCDF format, ensuring consistency and readiness for visualisation. The workflow is executed within the AWE and triggered at fixed times to ensure ingestion of newly available forecasts (Figure 14).

Once ingested, WAM wave forecasts are visualised directly in the Blue Insight environment as dynamic map layers (Figure 13). These layers can be explored interactively and combined with other datasets, such as vessel tracks or oceanographic fields, to provide integrated situational awareness. This enables users to assess evolving wave conditions in relation to fishing activity, safety considerations, and operational planning.

Figure 13. Visualisation of significant wave height forecast from WAM model in Blue Insight.

The screenshot displays the interface for the 'netcdf_split_opendap:1.1.0_imported_Testingcombine_load' flow. It includes a 'Flow Summary' section with the flow ID and 0 variables. A 'Recent Runs' section lists five completed runs with their IDs and timestamps. The 'Flow Configuration' section shows the flow name and tag. The 'Tasks' section lists three tasks: 'Get date for opendap filelink', 'Filter and download netcdf file using openDAP', and 'Combine newly created netCDF files', each using a 'dockerContainer'.

Figure 14. Screenshot of the WAM extraction service running in the AWE twice a day, at 05:15 UTC and 17:15 UTC, to generate a time series of selected parameters for the next 10 days and 5 days respectively.

3.5. New ecosystem model products from Disko Bay

New ecosystem model products developed for Disko Bay, West Greenland, represent a key scientific advance in support of Arctic fisheries and ecosystem-based management. The work builds on an existing high-resolution, three-dimensional ecosystem model implemented using the FlexSem unstructured modelling framework, which couples physical oceanography with biogeochemical and biological processes. The model integrates local observations from the GEM programme with large-scale forcing from Copernicus and other regional models, enabling realistic representation of circulation, sea²ice influence, and freshwater input in a complex Arctic coastal environment.

During the reporting period, the ecosystem model was significantly enhanced through improvements to numerical advection schemes and surface wind parameterisations, resulting in reduced numerical diffusion and more accurate representation of fronts and spatial gradients. These developments improved simulations of primary production, phytoplankton and zooplankton distributions, and their interannual

variability. Model outputs include multi-year spatial and temporal fields of nutrients, chlorophyll, phytoplankton and zooplankton biomass and production, providing the basis for new ecological indices relevant to fisheries planning.

In addition, a novel shrimp biophysical model was initiated to simulate larval dispersal and retention in Disko Bay by coupling biological traits with modelled circulation patterns. Together, these ecosystem products enable analysis of food-web dynamics, climate-driven variability, and potential impacts on key commercial species. When integrated into the digital platform, they support advanced visualisation and comparison with observational and fisheries-dependent data, strengthening the foundation for sustainable fisheries management in a rapidly changing Arctic environment.

May 23 2004

Figure 15. Modelled surface chlorophyll concentration on the 23rd of May 2004 from a) previous hydrodynamical model setup, and b) current model setup with new advection scheme. The white line marks an ice concentration of 10%.

4. Outreach and dissemination

During Year 2, DEC (Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication) activities focused on consolidating the project's visibility, strengthening engagement with priority target audiences, and establishing effective tools for communication and dissemination, in line with the DEC Plan. Building on foundations laid in Year 1, emphasis was placed on online presence, participation in strategic events, and systematic monitoring of performance through defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The **project website** functioned as the central information hub, providing up-to-date content on objectives, case studies, results, events, and outputs. Analytics from October 2024 to March 2026 show steady growth in traffic, with 445 unique users and recurring visits, indicating sustained interest. Usage peaks coincided with major external events, particularly Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP) symposia (Figure 16), demonstrating the importance of coordinated dissemination around high-visibility meetings. Cross-posting via partner websites further extended reach and helped direct traffic to the project platform.

Social media activity continued on LinkedIn and X, with LinkedIn emerging as the most effective channel for reaching professional audiences. Over 120 original posts were published across platforms, supported by strategic reposting from partners and SBEP channels. Audience growth, while moderate, showed clear increases around major announcements, such as endorsement by the UN Ocean Decade and participation in high-profile DTO-related events. Analytics indicate that the audience is primarily composed of researchers, business development professionals, and decision-makers, aligning well with the intended target groups.

Several **communication materials** were developed and actively used during Year 2. A multi-format project brochure was produced and translated into Danish and Icelandic (Figure 17), broadening accessibility in key regional contexts. A project poster was widely deployed at scientific and policy-oriented events, serving as an effective visual tool to communicate objectives and early progress. Both products were made openly available via Zenodo, supporting long-term visibility beyond individual events.

Engagement through events was a major component of Year 2 DEC activities. The project was represented at 16 conferences, workshops, symposia, and targeted meetings, most of them in person. These included SBEP meetings, European and Arctic-focused scientific conferences (Figure 18), DTO community events, and industry-relevant forums. Collectively, these activities reached several thousand participants across scientific, policy, industry, and innovation communities. Engagement with the scientific community and policy stakeholders was strong, providing a solid foundation for further expanding outreach to the fishing industry, media, and the general public as results mature.

Overall, Year 2 DEC activities successfully established the project's presence within relevant European and Arctic networks, created a solid suite of communication tools, and demonstrated measurable progress against KPIs. The report concludes that future DEC efforts should increasingly leverage emerging results and stakeholder networks to strengthen exploitation pathways and broaden societal impact.

ARCFISH at the Iceland Seafood Conference

From 6-7. Nov 2025, ARCFISH participated in the [Sjávarútvegsráðstefnan](#) (Seafood Conference Iceland), one of the leading events for the Icelandic seafood sector. The conference brought together fishers, processors, researchers, and policymakers to discuss innovation, sustainability, and the future of fisheries.

Sharing Arctic Fisheries Research

Þorsteinn Ágústsson, [Trackwell](#), presented our work on sustainable Arctic fisheries, including how data, environmental monitoring, and modelling can help manage fish stocks in a changing Arctic. The team highlighted approaches that combine scientific data with local knowledge to support decision-making and improve resilience in Arctic fisheries.

Connecting with Stakeholders

A key focus for ARCFISH at the conference was engaging with local fishers and industry stakeholders. Through discussions, the project explored practical ways to apply research findings to real-world fisheries management and strengthen collaboration across the Arctic seafood sector.

Science Meets Policy

The conference also offered an opportunity to share ARCFISH insights with European and Icelandic policymakers, helping bridge the gap between research and governance. Topics included sustainable resource use and the role of digital tools like digital twins of the ocean (DTO) in supporting fisheries decisions.

Looking Ahead

Participation in the Seafood Conference strengthens ARCFISH's commitment to innovation, collaboration, and sustainability in Arctic fisheries. Feedback and ideas from the conference will help guide the project's next steps and ensure its research remains relevant to both industry and policymakers.

Learn more about the conference here: [Sjávarútvegsráðstefnan](#)

Þorsteinn Ágústsson, Trackwell, provided a presentation about ARCFISH and visibility of Icelandic fisheries data in

Aarhus University and Kongsberg Discovery Showcase the ARCFISH Arctic Digital Twin at the Danish Marine Science Meeting 2026

Updated: 19 hours ago

ARCFISH partners [Kongsberg Discovery](#) and [Aarhus University](#) participated in the [23rd Danish Marine Science Meeting 2026](#), held on 20–22 January at the Konvention conference centre in Helsingør, Denmark. This annual conference, organised by Aarhus University ([Department of Ecoscience](#)) and [Ocean Institute](#), convened researchers, industry experts and public sector representatives to discuss current scientific advances and emerging challenges in marine science.

[Marie Maar](#), Aarhus University, presented, **"Decade of Ocean Science: Predictions and management scenarios using Digital Twins of the Ocean for Greenland, Faroe Islands and Denmark,"** highlighting how digital twins can be used to explore future ocean conditions and test management scenarios in the region. Her contribution illustrated how ARCFISH's tools can support decision-making by linking ecosystem simulations with real-world fisheries management questions.

[Vibe Schourup-Kristensen](#), Aarhus University, also presented, **"Modeling Shrimp Larval Drift in Disko Bay: Linking Ocean Dynamics and Recruitment in a Changing Arctic."** Her talk highlighted how ocean circulation and changing Arctic conditions shape the dispersal of shrimp larvae in Disko Bay, a key [case study site](#) for ARCFISH, offering important insights into the links between physical ocean processes and shrimp recruitment in a rapidly changing environment. Shrimp are an important part of marine food webs as they both feed on small organic particles and provide food for many larger species, helping transfer energy through the ecosystem. In this way, studying shrimp also helps researchers understand how changes in the Arctic may affect broader ecosystem productivity and fisheries.

Figure 18. ARCFISH participation in scientific conferences and industry events in 2025-2026. Left: Iceland Seafood Conference, November 2025. Right: 23rd Danish Marine Science Meeting 2026.

5. Future work

In the coming project phase, work will build directly on the extended data ingestion capabilities, new ecosystem model products, and stakeholder feedback developed during Year 2. Continued close collaboration with stakeholders—including fishers, seafood processors, researchers, resource managers, and policy-makers—will remain central to refining and validating the Arctic Fisheries Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO). Engagement will focus increasingly on demonstrating concrete use cases, collecting

targeted feedback on emerging data products, and supporting uptake through hands-on interaction with the platform.

From a technical perspective, further enhancements of the AWE will enable increased automation and scalability of data ingestion and processing. Planned developments include full automation of selected in situ data pipelines (e.g. Argo and GEM), extension of workflows to additional biogeochemical variables, and improved handling of spatio-temporal subsetting and derived indicators. Operational ingestion of CMEMS products, including TOPAZ5 and WAM forecasts, will be further stabilised and extended to support tailored products for the Greenland and Iceland case study regions.

Development of new data products will focus on advancing ecosystem-based indicators relevant for fisheries management. Outputs from the enhanced Disko Bay ecosystem model—including plankton dynamics and shrimp larvae dispersal—will be further analysed, validated against observations, and integrated into the DTO as candidate ecological indices. These products will be combined with in situ observations and fisheries-dependent data to support integrated analysis of environmental drivers, stock variability, and operational conditions.

The Digital Twin platform itself will continue to evolve, with emphasis on improved visualisation, comparison of multi-source datasets, and usability for non-technical users. Alpha testing results will be used to prioritise refinements of both functionality and user interfaces, supporting transition towards more mature, stakeholder-ready services.

Finally, dissemination and exploitation activities will increasingly leverage emerging scientific results and demonstrator products. Outreach will focus on targeted engagement with the fisheries sector and management authorities, complemented by continued presence at relevant scientific, policy, and industry events. These efforts will support preparation of a synthesis of DTO services and applications for Arctic fisheries, contributing to long-term impact and alignment with Sustainable Blue Economy objectives.

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